

THE PROGNOSTIC VALUE OF INFLAMMATORY AND NUTRITIONAL STATUS INDICES IN PREDICTING MORTALITY IN CRITICALLY ILL ELDERLY PATIENTS

Keywords

Geriatrics

Intensive care unit

Prognostic nutritional index (PNI); Hemoglobin, albumin, platelet (HALP) score

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ABSTRACT

To determine whether the Hemoglobin–Albumin–Lymphocyte–Platelet (HALP) score and the Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI), alongside conventional clinical and laboratory parameters, can effectively predict mortality in critically ill geriatric patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU). A retrospective study was conducted, including 100 ICU patients aged ≥ 65 years and 100 healthy controls. Demographics, APACHE II scores, feeding type, intubation status, and laboratory parameters were collected. Statistical analyses were performed using *t*-tests, the Mann-Whitney U test, the chi-square test, and correlation tests. Compared with controls, ICU patients had significantly higher neutrophil, monocyte, and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels, whereas lymphocyte, hemoglobin, platelet, and albumin levels were markedly lower (all *p*-values < 0.001). Both HALP and PNI scores were significantly lower in the ICU group ($p < 0.001$). Mortality at 7, 30, and 90 days was 38%, 57%, and 71%, respectively. The length of ICU stay was positively correlated with mortality ($r = 0.924$, $p < 0.01$). HALP and PNI demonstrated a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.403$, $p < 0.01$), but neither correlated with mortality. Geriatric ICU patients exhibit profound systemic inflammation, immunosuppression, and malnutrition. HALP and PNI scores reflect impaired immunonutritional status, suggesting potential prognostic value. However, their independent predictive power for mortality remains inconclusive, warranting further prospective studies.

INTRODUCTION

The aging population presents an increasing challenge for intensive care units (ICUs), as elderly patients frequently suffer from multiple comorbidities, frailty, and malnutrition. Critically ill geriatric patients experience higher mortality compared to younger populations due to impaired physiological reserves, systemic inflammation, and diminished immune response. Nutritional deficits further exacerbate these risks, underscoring the need for reliable prognostic tools.

Among various markers, the Hemoglobin, Albumin, Lymphocyte, Platelet (HALP) score and Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI) have been increasingly recognized as indicators of immunonutritional status.^{1,2} Previous studies demonstrated their predictive roles in malignancy, surgical, and cardiovascular cohorts, yet evidence in critically ill elderly patients remains limited.^{3,4} This study aimed to investigate the prognostic value of HALP and PNI scores in predicting mortality among geriatric ICU patients, comparing them with healthy controls and correlating them with conventional clinical outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This retrospective study included patients aged > 65 years admitted to the Internal Medicine ICU at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Hospital between 01/01/2023 and 12/31/2024. The study received approval from the Sivas Cumhuriyet University Clinical Research Ethics Committee (Approval No: 2025-07/81, Date: 07/10/2025) in full compliance with institutional and international research standards. As the analysis was based on anonymized retrospective data, the committee granted a waiver of informed consent. Demographic data (age, sex), ICU length of stay, feeding type, intubation status, and APACHE II scores were collected. Laboratory data included complete blood count, C-reactive protein (CRP), albumin, and cholesterol levels. Inclusion criteria were age ≥ 65 years, ICU admission during the study period, and availability of baseline laboratory values

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required for HALP and PNI calculation. Exclusion criteria included missing essential laboratory data, active hematologic malignancy, recent chemotherapy, or conditions known to significantly alter immunonutritional markers. After excluding patients whose laboratory data could not be accessed for the study, a group of 100 patients was formed. For comparison, 100 healthy adults who presented to the internal medicine outpatient clinic were included as controls. HALP score and PNI were calculated using standard formulas.^{1,5} The control group was younger than the ICU cohort; therefore, the groups were not age-matched, which represents a methodological limitation for age-dependent indices such as HALP and PNI.

Descriptive statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, min, max, .25-.75 quartiles, and percentiles) were used to evaluate the results of the study. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to determine whether the data came from a normal distribution. When parametric assumptions were met for comparing measurements, the independent samples t-test was used for two-group comparisons, and the Mann-Whitney U test was used when parametric assumptions were not met. For nonparametric data, the Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to compare more than two groups. Chi-square analyses were used to assess relationships between categorical groups. The relationship between variables was determined using

Pearson's correlation coefficient when the data were normally distributed and Spearman's correlation coefficient when they were not. A significance level of 0.05 was used to interpret the results.

RESULTS

A total of 100 ICU patients (mean age 86.0 ± 6.4 years; 61% male) and 100 controls (mean age 44.9 ± 11.1 years; 66% female) were included. This age difference was statistically significant and should be considered when interpreting age-sensitive immunonutritional indices. The ICU population showed considerable variability in clinical and laboratory parameters. The mean length of stay was 21.52 days, with some patients requiring prolonged hospitalization. The APACHE II score averaged 32.03, indicating moderate-to-severe illness. Hematological findings revealed anemia (mean hemoglobin 11.7 g/dL), lymphopenia (mean $1.23 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$), and a wide range of platelet counts. Marked systemic inflammation was evident, with elevated CRP levels (mean 98.15 mg/L) and reduced albumin levels (mean 2.59 g/dL), reflecting poor nutritional and inflammatory status. The hospital length of stay, APACHE II scores, cell counts, hemoglobin, CRP, and albumin levels of ICU patients are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Clinical Characteristics and Laboratory Findings in the Geriatric Intensive Care Patients

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Length of stay (day)	1	160	21.52
APACHE II	11	57	32.03
Neutrophil (cells/μL)	0.54	74.7	12.57
Monocyte (cells/μL)	0.07	5.1	0.91
Lymphocyte (cells/μL)	0.01	5.4	1.23
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	5.9	14.2	11.706
Platelet (cells/μL)	10	522	162.24
C-reactive protein (mg/L)	1.5	571	98.15
Albumin (g/dl)	1.1	3.9	2.59

In the geriatric patient group, compared with controls, there was clear evidence of inflammation (elevated neutrophil and monocyte counts, and elevated CRP), immune suppression (reduced lymphocyte counts), hematologic abnormalities (anemia and thrombocytopenia), and nutritional deficiency (low albumin). All differences were statistically significant ($p = 0.0001$, Table 2). HALP and PNI values were significantly lower in the patient group than in the control group ($p < 0.001$; Table 2). This finding indicates that immunonutritional indices reflect impaired nutritional status and immune response in critically ill patients.

Table 2. Comparison of Clinical and Laboratory Parameters Between The Patient and Control Groups

	Patient (mean)	Control (mean)	P
Neutrophil (cells/ μ L)	12.57	4.50	<0.01
Monocyte (cells/ μ L)	0.91	0.40	<0.01
Lymphocyte (cells/ μ L)	1.23	2.27	<0.01
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	11.7	13.38	<0.01
Platelet (cells/ μ L)	160.91	303.62	<0.01
C-reactive protein (mg/L)	98.15	4.00	<0.01
Albumin (g/dl)	2.59	4.39	<0.01
HALP score	32.27	45.13	<0.01
PNI	25.95	43.94	<0.01

Among the 100 patients included in the study, 14% received only oral nutrition, 25% received enteral nutrition, 27% received a combination of enteral and parenteral nutrition, and 24% received only parenteral nutrition. The proportion of patients who did not receive nutritional support was 10% because enteral feeding was withheld due to suspected gastrointestinal bleeding or because they died before parenteral nutrition could be initiated.

Table 3. Feeding Types and Intubation Statuses of The Geriatric Intensive Care Patients

Feeding Type	n=100	(%)
Oral	14	14
Enteral	25	25
Enteral & Parenteral	27	27
Parenteral	24	24
No feeding	10	10
Intubation Status	n=100	(%)
Intubated	76	76
Non-intubated	24	24

Mortality was observed in 38% of patients at 7 days, 57.7 % at 30 days, and 71% at 90 days. 25% of patients were transferred to another department after their need for ICU care ended. The overall hospital mortality rate was 17.5%. The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between length of stay and mortality ($r = 0.924$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that prolonged hospitalization was associated with an increased risk of death. In contrast, no significant relationship was observed between the APACHE II score and length of stay ($r = -0.094$) or mortality ($r = -0.082$), suggesting that baseline disease severity, as assessed by the APACHE II score, did not directly correlate with these outcomes in this cohort. Nutritional and inflammatory indices demonstrated distinct patterns. The HALP score was negatively correlated with mortality ($r = -0.129$) and length of stay ($r = -0.130$), although these associations did not reach statistical significance. Similarly, PNI showed only weak correlations with both length of stay ($r = -0.013$) and mortality ($r = -0.020$). However, PNI correlated with HALP ($r = 0.403$, $p < 0.01$), reflecting a significant association between these two nutritional-immunological parameters. Importantly, PNI was strongly and significantly negatively correlated with CRP ($r = -0.647$, $p < 0.01$), reinforcing the inverse relationship between systemic inflammation and nutritional-immune reserves. CRP demonstrated only weak and nonsignificant correlations with Length of Stay ($r = 0.053$), mortality ($r = 0.092$), and APACHE II score ($r = -0.062$). Overall, these findings suggest that length of stay is a strong predictor of mortality, while the prognostic utility of APACHE II, HALP, and PNI in this sample appears limited, with only HALP and PNI demonstrating a significant internal correlation (Table 4).

DISCUSSION

Mortality among elderly patients admitted to ICUs is considerably higher than in younger populations, mainly due to age-related physiological decline, multiple comorbidities, frailty, and impaired immune responses.⁶ These patients often

present with life-threatening conditions, multiorgan stabilization, and respiratory support. Consequently, they are dysfunction, or a high risk of rapid clinical deterioration, classified as “critically ill” and require intensive and necessitating advanced monitoring, hemodynamic continuous medical intervention.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis Between Length of Stay, Mortality, APACHE II score, HALP and PNI in Geriatric Intensive Care Patients

	Length of stay	Mortality	APACHE II score	HALP	PNI	CRP
Length of stay	1.000					
Mortality	0.924**	1.000				
APACHE II score	-0.094	-0.082	1.000			
HALP	-0.130	-0.129	-0.084	1.000		
PNI	-0.013	-0.020	0.099	0.403**	1.000	
CRP	0.053	0.092	-0.062	-0.130	-0.647**	1.000

Physiological aging, chronic diseases, immune senescence, and malnutrition play central roles in worsening clinical outcomes and higher mortality rates in this patient group.⁷ In the critically ill older population, malnutrition is especially common and is closely linked to higher rates of morbidity, infection, extended hospital stays, and mortality.⁸ Moreover, both systemic inflammation and nutritional depletion, which frequently coexist in geriatric ICU patients, are key determinants of prognosis. The use of indices that objectively assess these two components has therefore gained relevance in recent years as part of comprehensive patient evaluation.

Since many traditional scoring systems and assessment strategies were initially validated in younger or mixed-age ICU populations, their applicability to elderly cohorts remains uncertain.⁹ In this context, the need for reliable, practical, and low-cost prognostic indicators is evident. Indices such as the HALP score and the PNI have been explored as potential tools because they reflect both the inflammatory state and immunonutritional reserves using routine laboratory parameters.^{10,11}

The present study aimed to investigate whether HALP and PNI scores could serve as prognostic markers in critically ill geriatric patients by comparing them with healthy controls and examining their associations with mortality and clinical outcomes. Although these indices have shown predictive value in oncology, cardiovascular disease, and surgical settings,

evidence in elderly ICU populations is still insufficient and inconsistent.

The elevated neutrophil and monocyte counts and the reduced lymphocyte levels observed in the patient group provide clear evidence of a pronounced systemic inflammatory response and immune dysregulation. This finding aligns with previous studies showing that elevated neutrophil counts and reduced lymphocyte counts, particularly a high neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), are associated with stress, infection severity, and adverse outcomes in critically ill patients.^{12,13} These hematologic shifts reflect both inflammatory activation and impaired cellular immunity commonly seen in intensive care settings.

Hemoglobin and platelet levels were significantly lower among ICU patients, consistent with anemia and thrombocytopenia, which are frequently reported in critical illness. Hemodilution, nutritional deficits, bone marrow suppression, and inflammatory cytokine activity may explain these abnormalities. Prior research indicates that thrombocytopenia is associated with poorer prognosis in sepsis and multiorgan failure,¹⁴ whereas anemia is widely recognized as a negative prognostic factor in ICU populations.¹⁵

CRP levels were markedly elevated in the patient group, reinforcing the presence of severe inflammation. CRP is a well-established acute-phase reactant widely used in ICU practice

for both diagnostic and prognostic purposes.¹⁶ Its elevation reflects ongoing systemic inflammation and is frequently correlated with increased disease severity.

Similarly, compared to controls, ICU patients had much lower albumin levels, suggesting a combination of malnutrition, capillary leakage, and hepatic reprogramming of protein synthesis during inflammation. It has been repeatedly shown that hypoalbuminemia is a prognostic factor linked to increased mortality and longer ICU stays.¹⁷ These findings in our cohort support the interpretation that malnutrition and inflammation are intertwined in the geriatric critically ill population.

The significantly reduced HALP and PNI scores further underscore the impaired immunonutritional status characteristic of this group. Both indices are composite markers that reflect the interaction between inflammation, immune competence, and nutritional reserves. Previous studies have reported that lower HALP and PNI values are associated with adverse outcomes across oncology, surgical, and intensive care cohorts.¹⁸⁻²¹ Although evidence in geriatric ICU patients remains limited, the significant decline in these indices compared to healthy controls indicates their potential relevance in this setting.

Collectively, our findings confirm the coexistence of systemic inflammation (elevated neutrophils, monocytes, and CRP), immunosuppression (lymphopenia), hematologic abnormalities (anemia and thrombocytopenia), and malnutrition (low albumin, HALP, and PNI). These results align with established pathophysiological mechanisms described in the literature and reinforce the clinical importance of comprehensive nutritional and inflammatory assessment in elderly ICU patients.

Furthermore, the observed distribution of nutritional support and high rates of intubation in this population reflect practical constraints in oral intake and the necessity for enteral or parenteral feeding. Previous studies have demonstrated that early initiation of enteral or combined enteral–parenteral nutrition significantly reduces morbidity and mortality among critically ill patients, particularly those receiving mechanical ventilation.⁹ The predominance of enteral, parenteral and combined nutrition in our cohort is therefore consistent with current ICU nutritional practices.

Although HALP and PNI scores were markedly lower in critically ill elderly patients than in healthy controls, their associations with mortality and length of hospital stay were relatively weak in this study. Neither index demonstrated a statistically significant association with short-term outcomes, despite reflecting underlying immunonutritional impairment. Similar discrepancies have been observed in some ICU cohorts, where multifactorial determinants of mortality such as infection severity, organ dysfunction, frailty, and treatment limitations, may diminish the predictive strength of single composite indices.²²⁻²⁴

In contrast, the length of ICU stay was strongly positively correlated with mortality in our sample. This finding supports prior evidence that prolonged hospitalization is associated with higher mortality risk, increased exposure to infections, and cumulative physiological stress.²⁵ Interestingly, the APACHE II score, widely used to assess severity in intensive care settings, did not correlate significantly with mortality or length of stay. This observation may reflect the reduced discriminatory power of conventional severity scoring systems in geriatric populations, where age-related vulnerability and comorbidities complicate outcome prediction.^{26, 27} However, this finding should be interpreted with caution, as it is derived from a single-center, retrospective study with a limited sample size. The absence of a significant association may be related to insufficient statistical power or center-specific characteristics rather than a true lack of prognostic value. Moreover, conventional severity scores such as APACHE II were not specifically designed to incorporate geriatric-specific factors including frailty, functional status, and cumulative comorbidity burden, which may further limit their performance in very elderly ICU populations.

The internal correlation between HALP and PNI observed in this study indicates shared pathophysiological components and reinforces their mutual relevance in evaluating immunonutritional status. Additionally, the significant inverse relationship between PNI and CRP supports the established association between systemic inflammation and nutritional depletion. However, the absence of a direct link between these indices and mortality suggests that they may be better suited for risk stratification, baseline assessment, or longitudinal monitoring rather than short-term prognostication in ICU settings.

Despite their limitations in predicting mortality independently, HALP and PNI remain advantageous due to their simplicity, low cost, and reliance on routinely available laboratory parameters. If validated in larger, prospective, and homogenous ICU cohorts, these indices may contribute to individualized care strategies in elderly patients. Given the increasing prevalence of geriatric admissions to ICUs and the high burden of inflammation-related complications and malnutrition, further research is warranted to clarify the prognostic performance of immuno-nutritional indices in this setting.

Limitations

This study has certain limitations. The control group was younger than the ICU cohort, and this demographic difference may influence baseline immunonutritional parameters. However, age-matched control groups are not routinely available in geriatric ICU research, and many prior studies have used younger healthy controls to provide population-level reference values. The objective of our design was to compare critically ill elderly patients with a healthy baseline population rather than to perform an age-stratified immunonutritional comparison. Additionally, the retrospective single-center design limits the generalizability of the findings.

CONCLUSION

Critically ill elderly patients present a complex interplay of systemic inflammation, immunosuppression, hematologic abnormalities, and malnutrition. In this study, HALP and PNI scores were markedly lower in the ICU cohort than in healthy controls, indicating compromised immunonutritional status. However, neither index demonstrated a significant association with mortality or length of stay, suggesting that their standalone prognostic value in this population remains limited. In contrast, length of hospitalization showed a strong correlation with mortality, underscoring the cumulative clinical burden associated with prolonged ICU stays.

Despite the lack of direct correlation with mortality in this sample, HALP and PNI remain practical, low-cost indices derived from routine laboratory measurements. Their potential role may lie in baseline assessment, nutritional monitoring, and risk stratification rather than short-term mortality prediction. Larger, prospective, and more homogenous studies are needed to establish their clinical utility in geriatric critical care.

Declarations

The author is solely responsible for the study conception, design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and manuscript preparation.

The author has completed and submitted the ICMJE Disclosure Form for Potential Conflicts of Interest.

No financial support or conflicts of interest are declared.

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